

EXPRESSION OF THE CONCEPT OF PROMISE IN POLITICAL SPEECH

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Abstract: The speech act of promise can be accompanied by two other speech acts: encouragement and pledge. Moreover, since the main features of performative verbs, i.e. “I, you, here and now”, are present in promises, promise is also regarded as a performative act. In political promises, given the objectives of the discourse as well as the personal traits of the speaker, Most of political promises serve merely as advertising goals and are not intended to be fulfilled. The maxim of relevance is generally heeded in political promises and the violation of this maxim before elections is fairly rare. Political activists usually make use of efficient and influential manner of speech in their election campaigns.

Keywords: Speech act, promise, Political discourse,

Today, linguistics has different fields, aspects, and their structure is different new terms of the type are entering the science. A certain text, in particular, various methods for analyzing the literary text, referring to the above and tools we can use. For example, a cognitive-semantic approach to an artistic text or a content - essentially a given tariff - we can provide descriptions. This approach is a concept in itself requires us to apply. Cognitive linguistics is a linguistic representation of a certain concept in the world is a science that studies its essence and connection with world realities. And the concept one of the main categories of cognitive linguistics is culture and man is a connecting element between The term “concept” has been around since the 90s is used in linguistics. The concept concept is still a general one has no comment or interpretation. Concept is a modern term, originally a philosophy, in humanities such as linguistics, psychology, literary studies, cultural studies used. The concept concept in Russian linguistics in the first quarter of the 20th century introduced into scientific circulation by the philosopher S. Askoldov. He said to the concept, “It's a type or that reflects the process of thinking about other types of concepts [21,272]. If we connect the concept of a person, it is actual that is embodied around a person it can be understood that it expresses the sum of thoughts in one word. According to S. Askoldov, representatives of different nationalities communicate with each other through concepts. Creating and perceiving a concept is a two-way communication process. As you can see, the concept-concept is linguistically and culturally, determined on the basis of relationships between different cultures. But this term is used only when comparing or contrasting two nations should not be understood as Yu. S. Stepanov being intellectual in his studies to the etymology of the word concept, trying to reveal the essence of education applies. Concept is a derivative of the Latin word Conceptus. That is, in essence, this term corresponds to the word concept. And this term can be used not only between different languages or peoples, but also within one language. So this is a new term introduced by this tariff. we learned that we can use this word in the sense of a concept. After the need for the term increased and it began to be widely studied, the concept itself was

also emphasized that this is not the case. In particular, according to Yusupov's tariff: "The concept can be compared to an iceberg. If a concept is an iceberg, if there is one, then the part that sticks out of the water is the concept."

The concept itself from the point of view of cognitive linguistics, in particular cognitive semantics the question arises. Scientists evaluate this concept in different ways. According to N. Tikhonova: "A concept is a grammatical category that is related to its formal indicators and has distinctive features within that category." Nikitina M.V. noted: "The concept is discrete, multifactorial, and has a scholastic structure there is mental unity."

Summarizing many ideas about conceptual betting we can say the following:

1. A concept is "something" in the mind at a certain moment.
2. A concept is a higher level of abstraction of each element aspiring hierarchically organized structure.
3. The concept is a single whole, is the concept of a field whose elements are interconnected and in mutual movement connected.

The speech act of promise can be accompanied by two other speech acts: encouragement and pledge. Since, in this speech act, we have the concept of volunteer promise, and the speaker willingly makes a commitment to his/her addressee, according to George Austin's typology of speech acts, this speech act is considered to be an instance of commissive speech acts. Moreover, since the main features of performative verbs, i.e. "I, you, here and now", are present in promises, promise is also regarded as a performative act. In political promises, given the objectives of the discourse as well as the personal traits of the speaker, Grice's maxims – quality, quantity, relevance and manner – may be violated. In a political promise, there may be as much brevity as there is repetition. Most of political promises serve merely as advertising goals and are not intended to be fulfilled. The maxim of relevance is generally heeded in political promises and the violation of this maxim before elections is fairly rare. Political activists usually make use of efficient and influential manner of speech in their election campaigns.¹ It should be said that the concept of "promise" is a linguistic and cultural concept, which is expressed in human thinking and worldview. This linguistic and cultural concept is a universal feeling that has a significant impact on the formation and development of the qualities of nationality and humanity. Expression of the concept of "promise" by means of phraseological units, sentences, whole texts is considered a syntactic unit and a linguistic level that serves to understand its true essence. It is known that there are many concepts that are part of cultural speech and are actively used in speech activity at a certain level. They are distinguished by their presence in oral and written speech. One of the concepts with such a conceptual basis is the concept of "promise". The concept of "promise" is manifested in the important factors that determine the relationship between the speaker and the listener during the speech process.

Promising is a commissive speech act whose illocutionary force is that the speaker promises to do a future action to the benefit of a hearer by expressing its proposition (e.g., a promise) to the hearer (Searle, 1969). By promising, the speaker commits to doing this future action. Specifically, Searle (1969: 57-61) states nine conditions in total must be met in order for a promise to be successfully executed, which are paraphrased below: 1. The speaker and

¹ Shafaghi, M.. (2013). The speech act of "Promise" and "Promise in political discourse". 4. 141-158.

hearer must understand the language and the commitment meant by the speech act (i.e., it is not committed in a joking manner). 2. The speaker expresses the proposition. 3. The utterance of a promising speech act predicates a future action to be done by the speaker and no one else. 4. Under the preparatory condition, the hearer wants the promised future action done for them, and the hearer is aware of this desire. 5. Also under the preparatory condition, it is not obvious that the future action would have been done by the speaker prior to the act of promising. 6. The speaker intends to the future action under the sincerity condition, and he or she believes that the said action is possible for them to commit. 7. The speakers understands that the utterance of a promise will place him or her under obligation to commit the future, promised action under the essential condition. 8. The utterance of a promise is a semantic sign that transmits and expresses the intended promise, which is understood by the hearer as such. 9. The promise is correctly and sincerely uttered if and only if all other conditions are held.

With respect to its structure, previous researchers have proposed that promises have four primary types: direct, evasive, satirical, and conditional promises.² Additionally, Searle distinguishes between two IFIDs for promising: direct and indirect. The direct delivery of a promise contains the formula *I promise that..*, whereas evasive, satirical, and conditional promises represent indirect deliveries of a promise. Indirect strategies are also characterized by grammatical mood such as the imperative or conditional. Typically, direct promising predominates indirect strategies.

In the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language” the lexeme “promise” is mentioned as a word for doing or not doing something. In the Uzbek language, the concept of “promise” is expressed in noun and verb combinations such as “promise”, “term”, “to undertake”. It is known that “when creating a speech, a person is not only interested in its topic, but also expresses his feelings during the speech process. Emotions and inner experience in the speech process are formed as a private attitude of a person... a private emotional attitude, of course, originates from the mental state of the author of the text and is understood directly from the content of the text”³. The concept of “promise” is one of the internal feelings that “takes the main place in the relationship between two or more participants who have entered into a dialogue. The expressiveness of the use of the concept of “promise” in the speech process is shown as follows:

- creates a sense of trust between people;
 - increases the positive indicator of hard work;
 - strengthens mutual communication;
 - calls to be honest and fair, to acquire strong knowledge;
 - expands the process of independent thinking;
- determines the leading topic in communicative qualities that ensure the culture of speech.

² (Lyons, 1997; Kamel Al-Omari & Abu-Melhim, 2013; Nasser Saeidi, Yazdani Moghaddam, & Gharagozlou, 2014).

³ Hakimov M. O`zbek tilida matnning pragmatik talqini: filol. Fan. Doct. Diss. Toshkent. 2001. 34-35-b

References:

1. Shafaghi, M.. (2013). The speech act of "Promise" and "Promise in political discourse". 4. 141-158.
2. (Lyons, 1997; Kamel Al-Omari & Abu-Melhim, 2013; Nasser Saeidi, Yazdani Moghaddam, & Gharagozlou, 2014).
3. Hakimov M. O`zbek tilida matnning pragmatik talqini: filol. Fan. Doct. Diss. Toshkent. 2001. 34-35-p

